

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17839924>

TURKIY XALQLAR DOSTONLARINI QIYOSLAB O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Bugungi shiddat bilan rivojlanayotgan davrda yoshlarning intellectual salohiyati, fikrlash olamini rivojlantirish o'qituvchidan yuksak mas'uliyat talab qilishi shubhasizdir. Shu nuqtai nazardan uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida asrimizning zamonaviy yoshlariga an'anaviy qadriyatlardan yiroqlashmagan holda modernizatsiyalashtirilgan ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanib ta'lim va tarbiya bersih maqsadga muvofiq. baxshilarning epik repartuaridan joy olgan xalqning ming yillik an'ana va qadriyatlari tarannumi bo'lgan xalq eposlarining bor sehr-u jozibasi, badiiy g'oyasini o'quvchilarning tafakkur qatlariga qiyosiy tahlil orqali singdirishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning roli katta. Ushbu maqolada turkiy xalqlar dostonlaridagi obraz, syujet, yetakchi motivlarni qiyosiy tahlil asosida o'qitishda zamonaviy texnologiyalarning afzalliklari haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Turkiy xalq eposlari, qiyosiy tahlil, zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalar, modulli o'qitish, ta'limda sun'iy intellekt, epik motiv.*

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ПРИ СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОМ ОБУЧЕНИИ ЭПОСАМ ТЮРКСКИХ НАРОДОВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В стремительно развивающуюся эпоху современности формирование интеллектуального потенциала и мировоззрения молодёжи требует от педагога высокой ответственности. С этой точки зрения целесообразно осуществлять обучение и воспитание современного поколения, не отдаляясь от традиционных ценностей, используя модернизированные образовательные технологии в системе непрерывного образования. Современные технологии играют важную роль в том, чтобы через сравнительный анализ донести до

сознания учащихся художественную идею, многовековую традицию и ценностный потенциал народных эпосов, входящих в богатый эпический репертуар бахши. В данной статье рассматриваются преимущества применения современных технологий при сравнительном изучении образов, сюжетов и ведущих мотивов эпосов тюркских народов.

Ключевые слова. Тюркские народные эпосы, Сравнительный анализ, Современные образовательные технологии, Модульное обучение, Искусственный интеллект в образовании, Эпические мотивы и образы.

Advantages of Using Modern Educational Technologies in Comparative Teaching of the Epics of Turkic Peoples

ANNOTATION

In today's rapidly developing era, it is undeniable that cultivating the intellectual potential and cognitive worldview of youth requires great responsibility from educators. From this point of view, it is reasonable to provide education and upbringing to the modern youth of our century through modernized educational technologies without distancing them from traditional values within the continuous education system. Modern technologies play a significant role in introducing the artistic idea, the whole charm and magic of folk epics—which embody the thousand-year-old traditions and values of the nation and occupy an important place in the epic repertoire of bards—into students' thinking through comparative analysis. This article discusses the advantages of using modern technologies in teaching the images, plots, and leading motifs in the epics of Turkic peoples on the basis of comparative analysis.

Keywords: *Turkic folk epics, Comparative analysis, Modern educational technologies, Modular teaching, Artificial intelligence in education, Epic motifs and imagery, Multimedia-based learning.*

Introduction

In today's rapidly developing era, directing all the energy of active, curious children—those who never stop dreaming big in their small world and remain inquisitive about the hidden phenomena behind forbidden things—toward education and upbringing during the lesson depends directly on the pedagogical skill, knowledge, and methodology of the teacher. As our national leader emphasized, “The work being carried out to reform and improve the upbringing of youth on a modern basis, taking into account scientific and technological requirements, demands that it be shaped scientifically and spiritually in accordance with the needs of today. A new and systematic approach to upbringing is required: to fully reveal the social-pedagogical

potential of the family, preschool education, general education, secondary special vocational and higher educational institutions, and the community in forming fundamental qualities in children, and to raise the scientific-methodological coherence between them to a new level.”¹

Indeed, as modern technologies are rising to a leading position in every field in the digital world, their significance in education is also increasing dramatically. Generally speaking, the word “technology” originates from Latin and denotes “innovation.” The modernization of state educational standards, the improvement of textbooks, methodological manuals, programs, and classifiers related to the educational field is stimulating the introduction of new innovative practices. Any teaching technology that is directed toward a specific didactic purpose is based on a certain pedagogical idea. It prioritizes the development of various aspects of the individual. For this reason, the teacher-centered system in which students participate only as passive listeners has not proved effective in the continuous education system. The reason is that today’s generation cannot imagine life without the virtual world. They cannot sit passively for forty-five minutes. Turning them from passive listeners into active participants is one of the urgent problems in the education system.

Literature Review

Many folklorists and literary scholars have conducted research on folk epics. The historical significance and artistic value of Turkic epics are clearly reflected in the studies of scholars such as V. M. Zhirmunskiy, M. Tahmasib, A. Shamil, F. Bayat, S. Öztelli, and G. Snesarov. In addition, Sh. Turdimov’s book “*Obraz va talqin*” highlights the genesis, evolutionary stages, and leading motifs of folk epics. O. Ingyong’s dissertation titled “*Comparative Typology of the Epics Alpomish and Jumong*” examines the history of studying Uzbek and Korean epics and the comparative analysis of leading motifs in *Alpomish* and *Jumong*. N. Madrahimova’s dissertation “*Comparative-Typological Analysis of the Epic Shirin bilan Shakar*” provides information about plot similarities, interpretations, and typology of images and artistry in the Karakalpak and Uzbek versions of the epic. Z. Eshanova’s dissertation “*The Image of the Mountain in Uzbek Folk Epics: Its Genesis and Artistic Interpretations*” analyzes the evolutionary stages, genesis, and mythological aspects of the mountain image from myth-ritual-epic and comparative-typological perspectives. In N. Yusufjonova’s dissertation “*Technology of Teaching Turkic Folk*

¹ Mirziyoyev, Sh. We Will Build a Free and Prosperous Democratic Uzbekistan Together. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2016, p. 50.

Epics on the Basis of Comparative-Typological Approach,” shared artistic features and epic motifs in Uzbek, Kyrgyz, Kazakh, and Turkmen epics are discussed.

Research Methodology

This article focuses on the advantageous aspects of modern technologies in teaching leading motifs, plots, and images in the epics of Turkic peoples through comparative analysis. In particular, the newest technologies are compared with traditional lessons in transforming students from passive listeners into active participants. The role of artificial intelligence, multimedia tools, modular and problem-based educational technologies in comparative teaching is illustrated through folk epics. Methodological aspects of comparative analysis that provide convenience in conducting artistic analysis are also examined.

Analysis and Results

In the early twentieth century, as mobile communication tools entered our lives and became widespread, we could hardly imagine life without social networks; now, without artificial intelligence, we cannot perform our tasks quickly and efficiently. In literary education, artificial intelligence can be used effectively in teaching folk epics through comparative analysis. Teaching the most essential ideological points of lengthy epics through analytical exercises helps to appropriately allocate class time. For example, animating characters in the epic *Ravshan*, giving them voices, and creating animated video clips using the “MyHeritage” application develops creativity, imaginative thinking, and research competencies, and contributes to elevating literature to the level of art. Additionally, the teacher may choose one of the frequently occurring detail-images (letter, ring, bird, horse, bow) in epics and conduct the “Torrance Test.” A student, seeing various shapes on the board, draws one of the detail-images from folk epics based on their individual interpretation and, using ChatGPT, presents in tables or diagrams which other folk epics also feature this image. This technology requires quick thinking, strong memory, and ability.

Dividing students into groups and assigning them to prepare a presentation in “Canva” about similar plot lines and motifs in folk epics develops their creative abilities. As stated, “Creativity is an irreplaceable and unique ability that requires thinking at an artistic level. However, in reality, it is simply finding straightforward solutions to seemingly complex problems.” While describing their presentations, the teacher announces the following rules:

- Adherence to presentation time regulations;
- Observance of presentation order;
- Pre-distribution of tasks among group members;
- Ensuring high-quality design in creating the presentation corpus;
- Paying special attention to students’ speech.

Overall, artificial intelligence has many advantages, but not all the information it provides is accurate. Moreover, it cannot feel a literary work like a human, nor can it perceive the emotions within characters' inner worlds. "Artificial intelligence automates the system of evaluating knowledge, pushing human factors aside. It facilitates the tedious tasks of checking homework and grading tests. In essence, no artificial intelligence can ever replace the lively interaction of a teacher, though it may come close. However, drawing positive and creative ideas from artificial intelligence and using pedagogical mastery, a teacher will undoubtedly find a path to the hearts of modern generations."

Forming in students competencies to feel—not merely describe—that folk epics embody noble qualities such as love for the motherland, respect for parents, bravery and perseverance characteristic of men, loyalty of women, and the sacredness of family, is greatly facilitated by modular teaching technologies. According to sources, the term "modular teaching" is an international concept (from the Latin *modulus*), meaning a unit consisting of interrelated elements capable of functioning. The significant advantage of this innovative technology is that it allows individualization of curricula according to each student's abilities and interests. Consequently, this approach reduces lengthy and tedious lectures, giving priority to students' thinking and independent learning. To improve the teaching of Turkic folk epics through comparative methods, the modular teaching technology may be organized as follows:

1. Module Objective – Topic-Based Outcomes. In the 11th-grade literature curriculum, studying the epic "*The Birth of Gorogly*" aims to identify "traditional epic motifs," to find "similar plot scenes in the epics of related peoples," and to create "a typological comparison of images through literary portraits and descriptions." In doing so, the teacher develops each student's abilities in remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, synthesizing, and self-assessment.

2. Main Content of the Topic. Before completing this module, students must be divided into two or three groups. Grouping should be fair; placing weaker students in one group and stronger students in another may negatively affect psychological motivation. The "Random" application helps ensure fairness. Lessons structured as competitions and discussions encourage students to be inquisitive and to think not only about themselves but also about group honor. To help students understand the main content of "*The Birth of Gorogly*", the teacher must follow the principle of systematicity. Before reading, the teacher may ask questions such as: "Why do you think the epic is titled this way? How can a dead person be reborn?" and "Do you believe in supernatural births? Have you encountered such cases in life?" These questions prepare students for reading and increase interest.

3. Teaching and Learning Methods. In this module, students answer theoretical questions based on their reading of the epic. Using the “Insert” method, while reading the assigned passages, students mark symbols (“* – I know,” “+ – new information,” “– I don’t understand,” “? – I want to know more”). This reveals the depth of their thinking and the analysis of stored knowledge.

4. Learning Tasks and Exercises. Each group is assigned a project—to create a “Literary Anthology.” Multimedia tools may be used. The first group compares the contemporary variants of expressions found in the epic *Gorogly*. The second group compares similar elements of composition with other folk epics. The third group explains the uniqueness of motifs and their artistic functions through comparative evidence. The teacher emphasizes timely completion and creative approaches. This module fosters practical skills through creative thinking and contributes directly to achieving module outcomes.

5. Assessment Criteria During and After the Module. Assessment is crucial in modular teaching. It evaluates student activity, knowledge, and speech. Diagnostic tests, communicative and analytical questions, and group evaluations are used. To assess mastery of “*The Birth of Gorogly*”, the “I assess myself” method is recommended. Each student receives anonymous questions:

-Marking “yes or no” to ten statements in the section “Today I found answers to the following questions.”

-Explaining difficulties faced, reasons, and expected assistance in the section “I encountered challenges.”

-Indicating expectations for the next lesson in the section “I want to improve myself.”

-Giving suggestions and conclusions in the final question.

The advantages of this module include developing students’ ability to analyze shared artistic features in folk epics through comparative approaches, working effectively with modern information resources, familiarizing them with advanced innovative methods, and shaping their competencies.

At the same time, students’ visualization of scenes from folk epics cannot be achieved simply by reading short excerpts. Organizing virtual tours of folk epics, screening films such as “*Alpomish*” and “*Gorogly*” increases their interest, brings them closer to the psychological world of the ideal protagonist, and strengthens universal qualities such as perseverance and bravery. It also supports the idea that high-school students, who already spend less time on play and more on serious tasks, enjoy completing academic work independently, and that students’ interest in lessons depends on the teacher’s method of instruction.

Conclusion

In short, effective use of modern technologies not only ensures that literary education keeps pace with the times, but also helps form students' competencies in analyzing the leading ideas of folk epics through comparative methods, increases their activity, saves time, and enables efficient use of information resources. Moreover, it strengthens the principles of cooperation between teacher and student and reinforces the idea that modern technologies will always aid in comparing the leading ideas in folk epics with real-life examples.

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